

GREEN SYNTHESIS OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES USING STERCULIA QUADRIFIDA LEAF EXTRACT

*Dissertation submitted to the University of Kerala in partial fulfillment of
the requirements for the award
of the degree of*

Master of Science

in

Physics

by

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Date: 23 August 2017

Bishop Moore College

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2015-2017

PREFACE

Nanotechnology is an emerging field dealing with the fabrication and engineering of materials, structures and systems with nano-scale at least in one dimension. People are interested in the nano scale because it is at this scale that the properties of materials can be very different from those at a larger scale. Nanoparticles of noble metals have received great interest due to the properties associated to their nanometre dimensions. Silver is an especially attractive metal due to its remarkable size and shape depend optical properties , highest efficiency of Plasmon excitation and highest electrical and thermal conductivity in the bulk among all metals.

The present work entitled “**Green Synthesis and Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles using Sterculia Quadrifida Leaf Extract**” deals with the synthesis and the study of the absorption and photo luminescence properties of colloidal silver nanoparticles. The size of the particles was determined using transmission electron microscopy.

The first chapter contains a brief introduction to nanoparticles, their classification, main properties and some of their applications.

The second chapter deals with the different preparation and characterization techniques of colloidal silver nanoparticles.

Third chapter gives the details of preparation of colloidal silver nanoparticles, Absorption and Emission studies of the synthesized colloidal silver nanoparticles and the morphology of the particles. Antibacterial and Anticancerous studies were also conducted.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Nanoscience implies a scale of measurement that exists at the level of the nanometer (1). Nanoscience is the study of phenomena and manipulation of materials at atomic, molecular and macromolecular scales, where properties differ significantly from those at larger scale (2). Nanotechnology comprises the emerging applications of nanoscience (3). Nano technology is the design, characterization, production and application of structures, devices and systems by controlling shape and size at nanometer scale (2). The etymological derivation of the prefix ‘nano’ can be traced back to the latin ‘nanus’ and further back to the Greek root ‘nan(n)os’ which means dwarf or “little old man”. Nanotechnology therefore is a technology defined by the nanometer. 1nm is equivalent to one-billionth of a meter (10^{-9} m) (1). A human hair is approximately 80,000nm wide, and a red blood cell approximately 7000nm wide atoms are below a nanometer in size, whereas many molecules, including some proteins, range from a nanometer upwards (2). The conceptual underpinnings of nanotechnologies were first laid out in 1959 by the physicist Richard Feynman, in his lecture, ‘There’s plenty of room at the bottom’. Feynman explored the possibility of manipulating material at the scale of individual atoms and molecules (2).

People are interested in the nanoscale because a number of physical phenomena become noticeably pronounced as the size of the system decreases. As Feynman said “when we have some control of the arrangement of things on a molecular scale, we will get an enormously greater range of possible properties that substances can have”, and these new properties will lead to a wide variety of applications which we cannot even envisage today. Materials reduced to the nanoscale can suddenly show very different properties such as electrical conductivity, elasticity, greater strength, different color and greater reactivity-characteristics that the very same substances do not exhibit at the micro or macro scales. These properties are largely due to two factors. First, the nano materials have a relatively larger surface area when compared to the same mass of materials produced in the larger form, making them much more chemically reactive. Second, quantum effects can begin to dominate the behavior of matter at the nanoscale

affecting the optical, electrical and magnetic qualities of materials in unpredictable ways (4). In some cases, size-dependent properties have been exploited for centuries. For example, gold and silver nanoparticles (particle of diameter less than 100nm) have been used as coloured pigments in stained glass and ceramics since the 10th century AD(2).

The field of nanotechnology is one of the most active areas of research in modern materials science. Nanoparticles exhibit completely new or improved properties based on specific characteristics such as size, distribution and morphology. Nanotechnology is a field that is bargaining day by day, making an impact in all spheres of human life. New applications of nanoparticles and nanomaterials are emerging rapidly. Nanocrystalline silver particles have found tremendous applications in the field of high sensitivity biomolecular detection and diagnostics, antimicrobials and therapeutics, catalysis and micro-electronics (6).

1.2 Top down and bottom up approaches

The nanotechnology literature often focuses on the structure size and differentiates between two basic approaches. The top-down approach tries to enhance the methods from microtechnology to achieve structure sizes in the medium and also lower nanometer range. This approach is based on a physical and microlithographic philosophy, which is in contrast to the other approach, where atomic or molecular units are used to assemble molecular structures, ranging from atomic dimensions up to supramolecular structures in the nanometer range. This bottom-up approach is mainly influenced by chemical principles (7).

The alternative of 'top down' and 'bottom up' approaches was first discussed in the context of different types of software development in the information sciences. These terms were transferred to nanotechnology in order to facilitate a distinction between the way down from macro and micro objects through miniaturization to the molecular level and a strategic handling of atoms, molecules and nano objects considered as natural entities. The latter ought to be aware of quantum physical laws and it lead to certain new situations somehow located between quantum and classical physics. Some experts entertain the hope that these new ways of building new objects will be added to the familiar methods of synthetic chemistry (8).

The challenge of modern nanotechnology is the realization of synthesis by the top-down and bottom-up approaches. This task is not driven entirely by the absolute structural dimensions, because today macro and supramolecules extending up to hundreds of nanometers or even micrometers can already be synthesized or isolated from biological systems. So the overlap of both approaches is not a problem. Both techniques provide specific capabilities that can be implemented by the other (7).

The bottom-up approach promises a better chance to obtain nanostructures with less defects, more homogeneous chemical composition and better short and long range ordering, because this approach is mainly driven by the reduction of Gibbs' free energy (9).

1.3 Nanostructured materials

With the emergence of nanotechnology and nanoscience investigation and application of nanostructured materials is growing rapidly (2). Nanostructured materials are materials with structural dimensions between 1-100nm. Materials that have one dimension in the nanoscale are layers, such as thin films or surface coatings. Some of the features on computer chips come in this category. Materials that are nanoscale in two dimensions include nanowires and nanotubes. Materials that are nanoscale in three dimensions are particles, for example precipitates, colloids and quantum dots (10).

Nanostructured materials may be grouped under nanoparticles (the building blocks), nanointermediates, and nanocomposites. They may be in or far away from thermodynamic equilibrium. The various classes of nanoparticles that serve as the building blocks of nanomaterials and devices include nanocrystalline materials such as ceramic, metal and metal oxide nanoparticles'; fullerenes, nanotubes and related structures; nanofibers and wires and precise organic as well as hybrid organic-inorganic nanoarchitectures such as dendrimers and polyhedral silsesquioxanes, respectively (2, 11, 12).

1.3.1 Nanocrystalline materials

Nanocrystalline materials include ceramics, metals and metal oxide nanoparticles. These materials are assembled from nanometer sized building blocks, mostly crystallites. The building blocks may differ in their atomic structure, crystallographic orientation, or chemical composition. In cases where the building blocks are crystallites, incoherent or coherent interfaces may be formed between them, depending on the atomic structure, the crystallographic orientation, and the chemical composition or adjacent crystallites. In other words, materials assembled of nanometer-sized building blocks are micro structurally heterogenous, consisting of the building blocks (eg.crystallites) and the regions between adjacent building blocks (eg.grain boundaries) (2, 11).

Nanocrystallites of bulk inorganic solids have been shown to exhibit size dependent properties, such as lower melting points, higher energy gaps, and nonthermodynamic structures. In comparison to macroscale powders, increased ductility

has been observed in nanopowders of metal alloys. In addition, quantum effects from boundary values become significant leading to such phenomena as quantum dots lasers (2).

1.3.2 Carbon nanotubes / Fullerenes

The discovery of fullerenes in 1985 by Curl, Kroto, and Smalley culminated in their Nobel Prize in 1996. Fullerenes, or Buckminster Fullerenes, are named after Buckminster Fuller the architect and designer of the geodesic dome and are sometimes called bucky balls. The names derive from the basic shape that defines fullerenes; an elongated sphere of carbon atoms formed by interconnecting six-member rings and twelve isolated five-member rings forming hexagonal and pentagonal faces. The first isolated and characterized fullerene, C-60, contains hexagonal faces and 12 pentagonal faces just like a soccer ball and possesses perfect symmetry. Fullerene chemistry continue to be an exciting field generatying my articles with promising new applications every year (2).

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were first isolated and characterized by Ijima in 1991. CNTs are hollow cylinders of carbon atoms. Their appearance is that of rolled tubes of graphite such that their walls are hexagonal carbon rings and are often formed in large bundles. The ends of CNTs are domed structures of six-membered rings capped by a five-membered ring. Generally speaking, there are two types of CNTs: single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs) and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs). As their names imply, SWNTs consist of a single, chlindrical grapheme layer, whereas MWNTs consist of multiple grapheme layers telescoped about one another. The unique physical and chemical properties of ANTs, such as structural rigidity and flexibility continue to generate considerable interest. CNTs are extremely strong, about 100 times stronger than steel at one-sixth the weight. CNTs can also act as either conductors or semiconductors depending on their chirality, possess an intrinsic superconductivity, are ideal thermal conductors and can also behave as field emitters (1,2).

1.3.3 Dendrimers (Organic nanoparticles)

The term dendrimer is derived from a combination of two Greek words: “Dendron”, meaning tree or branch, and “meros”, meaning part. It refers to a vast class of large molecular architectures that contain structurally perfect, highly branched

nanostructures (13). A dendrimer is an artificially manufactured or synthesized large molecule comprised of many smaller ones linked together built up from branched units called monomers. Technically, dendrimers are a unique class of a polymer, about the size of an average protein, with a compact, tree like molecular structure, which provides a high degree of surface functionality and versatility. Their shape gives them vast amounts of surface area, making them useful building blocks and carrier molecules at the nanoscale and they come in a variety of forms, with different physical and chemical properties (14, 2).

1.3.4 Inorganic-organic hybrid nanoparticles

Hybrid inorganic-organic composites are an emerging class of new materials that hold significant promise. Materials are being designed with the good physical properties of ceramic and the excellent choice of functional group chemical reactivity associated with organic chemistry. New silicon containing organic polymers, in general, and polysilsesquioxanes, in particular, have generated a great deal of interest because of their potential replacement for and compatibility with currently employed, silicon-based inorganics in the electronics, photonics, and other materials technologies. Hydrolytic condensation of trifunctional silanes yields network polymer or polyhedral clusters having the generic formula $(\text{RSiO}_{1.5})_n$. Hence they are known by the “not quite on the tip of the tongue” name silsesquioxanes. Each silicon atom is bound to an average of one and a half (sesqui) oxygen atoms and to one hydrocarbon group (ane). Typical functional groups that may be hydrolyzed / condensed include alkoxy or chlorosilanes, silanols and silanols.

These inorganic-organic hybrids offer a unique set of physical, chemical and size dependent properties that could not be realized from just ceramics or organic polymers alone. Silsesquioxanes are therefore depicted as bridging the property space between these two component classes of materials. Many of these silsesquioxane hybrid materials also exhibit an enhancement in properties such as solubility, thermal and thermomechanical stability, mechanical toughness, optical transparency, gas permeability, dielectric constant and fire retardancy (2,15).

1.3.5 Nano-Intermediates

Nanostructured films, dispersions, high surface area materials and supramolecular assemblies are the high utility intermediates to many products with improved properties such as solar cells and batteries, sensors, catalysts, coatings and drug delivery systems. They have been fabricated using various techniques. Nanoparticles are obvious building blocks of nano systems but, require special techniques such as self-assembly to properly align the nanoparticles. Recent developments have lead to air resistant, room temperature systems for nanotemplates with features as small as 67nm. More traditionally, electron-beam systems are used to fabricate devices down to 40nm (2).

1.3.6 Nanocomposites

Nanocomposites are materials with a nanoscale structure that improve the macroscopic properties of products. Typically nanocomposites are clay, polymer or carbon, or a combination of these materials with nanoparticle building blocks. Nanocomposites materials with nanoscale separation of phases can generally be divided into two types: multilayer structures are typically formed by gas phase deposition or from the self-assembly of monolayers. Inorganic / organic composites can be formed by sol-gel techniques, bridging between clusters as in silsequioxanes, or by coating nanoparticles, in polymer layers for example nanocomposites can greatly enhance the properties of materials for example, ppm level impurities can result in the formation of nanoscale aluminide secondary phases in aluminum alloys, increasing their strength and corrosion resistance. Magnetic mltilayered materials are one of the most important aspects of nanocomposites as they have led to significant advances in storage media (2).

1.3.7 Polymer-clay nanocomposites

The large industrial demand for polymers has lead to an equally large interest in polymer composites to enhance their properties. Clay-polymer manocompsites are among the most successful nanotechnological materials today. This is because they can simultaneously improve material properties without significant tradeoffs. Recent efforts have focused upon polymer-layered silica nanocomposites and other polymer o clay

composites. These materials have improved mechanical properties without the large loading require by traditional particulate fillers. Increased mechanical stability in polymer-clay nanocomposites also contributes to an increased heat deflection temperature. These composites have a large reduction gas and liquid permeability and solvent uptake. Traditional polymer composites often have a marked reduction in optical clarity; however, nanoparticles cause little scattering in the optical spectrum and very little ultraviolet scattering. Although flame retardant additives to polymers typically reduce their mechanical properties, polymer-clay nanocomposites have enhanced barrier and mechanical properties and are less flammable compression-injection moulding and melt-interaction and coextrusion of the polymer with ceramic nanopowders can form nanocomposites. Often no solvent or mechanical shear is needed to promote intercalation (2, 16).

1.4 Nanoparticles

Nanoparticles are defined as particle of less than 100nm in diameter (2). Nanoparticles are viewed as the fundamental building blocks of nanotechnology. They are the starting points for preparing many nanostructured materials and devices. Their synthesis is an important component of the rapidly growing research efforts in nanoscience and nanoengineering (5, 17). Nanoparticle exhibit new or enhanced size-dependent properties compared with larger particles of the same material. Nanoparticles exist widely in the natural world: for example as the products of photochemical and volcanic activity and created by plants and algae (2). Nanoparticles have attracted considerable and increasing attention in the academic research area and industry last few decades. Because of the novel physical and chemical properties different from bulk systems, nanoparticles are used in a variety of material science and engineering such as optics, electronics, magnetic media and catalysis (18-23). The most important and distinct property of nanoparticles is that they exhibit larger surface area to volume ratio. The most effectively studied nanoparticles today are those made from noble metals, in particular silver, platinum, gold and palladium (9). Among various metal nanoparticles, silver nanoparticles are of special interest due to their unique optical and electrical properties, as well as for their potential biomedical applications (24-26).

1.4.1 Metal nanoparticles

Nanoparticles of metals have been investigated extensively in recent years due to their novel material properties which differ greatly from the bulk substances (27). The history of metal nanoparticles begins with Faraday's study of gold colloids. Metal nanoparticles play important roles in many different areas. They can serve as a model system to experimentally probe the effects of quantum confinement on electronic, magnetic and other related properties. They have also been widely exploited for use in photography, catalysis, biological labeling, photonics, optoelectronics, information storage, surface enhanced Raman scattering and formulation of magnetic ferrofluids. The intrinsic properties of metal nanoparticles are mainly determined by its size, shape, composition crystallinity and structure (28). These properties are dominated by the strong Surface Plasmon Resonances (SPRs) of the metal nanoparticles. Surface plasmons (SPs) are waves that propagate along the surface of a conductor, usually metals due to their large but negative dielectric constant. Surface plasmons are essentially light waves that are trapped on the surface because of their interaction with the free electrons of the conductor. In this interaction, the free electrons respond collectively by oscillating in resonance with the light wave. The spectral position of the SPRs in the compound materials can be designed within a wide spectral range covering the visible and near-infrared spectra. This makes the compound materials very promising candidates for the applications in the field of photonics. Due to surface Plasmon excitation, nanoparticles of silver, gold and copper may exhibit sharp electronic absorption bands in the visible region (29, 30). Gold, silver and copper nanoparticles exhibit Plasmon resonances at 520nm, 385nm and 560nm respectively (8). The synthesis of metal nanoparticles is described in several excellent reviews. Both organic and aqueous solvents are used to produce metal nanoparticles with tunable sizes (31).

1.4.1.1 Optical properties of metal nanoparticles

A reduction in particle size leads to different physical and especially optical properties. Reducing the size of the nanoparticles has a pronounced effect on the energy level spacing as the system becomes more confined. The energy spacing between adjacent levels increases with decreasing dimensions. Quantum size effects are also known for metal nanoparticles. The light scattering by nanometer-sized metal particles

is dominated by the collective oscillation of the conduction electrons induced by the incident electric field, known as the surface Plasmon resonance. The surface Plasmon resonance does not give rise to the most intense absorption of very small clusters but is rather strongly damped. The surface plays a very important role for the observation of the surface Plasmon resonance as it alters the boundary conditions for the polarizability of the metal and therefore shifts the resonance to optical frequencies. The specific color of the scattered light is a function of the size, shape and material properties of the particle. Silver or gold Plasmon resonance particles with diameters of 30-120nm efficiently scatter light in the visible region of the electromagnetic spectrum (31,8,29).

1.4.2 Silver

The atomic number of silver is 47. Its electronic configuration is $[\text{Kr}] 4d^{10} 5s^1$. Silver is a group 11, period 5 transition metal. Silver, it is said, is one of nature's 92 chemically pure elements with proven benefits for man while being toxic to all species of bacteria, fungi, protozoa, parasites and a number of viruses. Of late, this wonder metal is slowly gaining ground as a therapeutic element in the form of colloidal silver. Believers of this novel form of alternative therapy, meanwhile, continue to profess of its amazing curative powers. Silver possesses the highest electrical and thermal conductivity.

1.4.3 Nanostructured silver

Materials of single metals usually demonstrate unique properties. When such nanostructured materials meet complex structured natural substances, highly functional materials are created. The growth of metal on biomolecular templates is a promising route to producing complex metal nanostructures. Silver nanoparticles were first used to transcribe a single biopolymer strand by Braun et al. In this case, a single strand of derivatized DNA was bridged between two gold electrodes, followed by reduction of the latter with hydroquinone to exchange the DNA Na^+ counter ions for Ag^+ ions. In this way, small Ag particles were formed on the DNA template. Subsequently, more silver was deposited on this DNA-Ag strand by standard photographic procedures, resulting in a thin wire built up of small silver grains which presented interesting hysteric I-V curves. Thinner wires were also produced by this method. In later work one-dimensional metallic, semiconducting and magnetic nanoparticles arrays as well as nanowires with diameters as small as 15 nm and displaying a variety of physicochemical properties such

as metallic, fluorescent, magnetic and even binary semiconductors were successfully reported with good control over the dimensions, crystallinity and even chirality (5).

Nanoparticles of noble metals have received great interest due to properties associated to their nanometer dimensions. Silver is an especially attractive metal due to its remarkable size and shape dependent optical properties, highest efficiency of Plasmon excitation and highest electrical and thermal conductivity in the bulk among all metals. These special properties have led to promising applications of silver nanoparticles in catalysis for the selective oxidation of styrene, environmentally friendly antimicrobial coatings, real time optical sensors, printed electronics, photonics and so on (32). Silver nanoparticles show better optical properties due to the sharpness of their Plasmon absorption band at wavelengths that are strongly dependent on the medium in which the particles are present. Their sharp Plasmon resonance has been employed for the enhancement of Raman's signals for replacing fluorescents markers of biological events and in photographic process. These applications require aqueous silver colloidal solutions (33, 34).

1.5 Colloidal silver

Colloidal silver is a suspension of submicroscopic metallic silver particles in a colloidal base (35). Colloidal particles are larger than molecules but too small to be observed directly with a microscope; however their shape and size can be determined by electron microscopy. Colloidal particles are usually on the order of 10^{-7} to 10^{-5} cm. Interest in the optical properties of colloidal metals dates back to Roman times. Nanosized gold particles were often used as colorants in glasses and quite complex optical effects were created using metal particles. In the seventeenth century, "Purple of Cassius", a colloid of heterocoagulated tin dioxide and gold particles, became a popular colorant in glasses. These early manifestations of unusual colors of colloidal gold in the middle of the last century. Today his studies are generally considered to mark the foundations of modern colloid science. The formation of color centers and small colloidal metal particles in ionic matrices and glasses has remained an area of very active research, driven, in part, by the technical importance of the photographic process. The more recent discovery that the surface Plasmon absorption band also provide information on the development of the band structures in metals has led to a plethora of

studies on the dependent optical properties of metal particles, particularly those of silver and gold while advances in molecular beam techniques now enable spectroscopic analysis of metal clusters to be carried out in vacuum (36-38).

1.5.1 Properties of colloids

A substance is said to be in the colloidal state, when it is dispersed in another medium in the form of very small particles having diameter between 10^{-4} to 10^{-7} cm. Thus, the size of particles in a colloidal state may be regarded as an intermediate between molecular size 10^{-7} cm to 10^{-8} cm and particles of a coarse suspension 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} cm. Colloidal solution may be considered as a heterogeneous system consisting of three essential components.

1. A dispersed phase
2. A dispersion medium or continuous phase or the outer phase and
3. A stabilizing agent

Thus a colloidal solution is one in which a definite substance is distributed in the form of very small particles of a diameter between 10^{-4} to 10^{-7} cm as dispersed phase in another substance called the dispersion medium.

Dispersed phase + Dispersion medium = Dispersion system (Colloidal solution)

Each of the two phases constituting a colloidal system may be a gas, a liquid or a solid. The term sol is applied to the dispersion of a solid in a liquid, solid or gaseous medium. The dispersion of a solid in a liquid is termed as colloidal solution. The dispersion of a solid in a gas is termed as a solid aerosol. If the dispersed phase is a liquid and the dispersion medium a gas, the resulting sol is called a liquid aerosol. When a liquid is dispersed in another liquid the resulting system is called an emulsion. If colloidal system becomes fairly rigid, it is termed as gel.

The properties associated with colloids are,

Heterogeneous nature

Colloidal solutions are heterogeneous in nature consisting of two distinct phases viz, the dispersed phase and the dispersion medium. Experiments like dialysis, ultra

filtration and ultra centrifuging, clearly indicate the heterogeneous character of colloidal system.

Non-settling nature

Colloidal solutions are quite stable. The suspended colloidal particles remain suspended in the dispersion medium indefinitely. In other words there is no effect of gravity on the colloidal particles. A gold sol was prepared by Faraday in 1867. This sol is still present in the museum of London without any detectable settling.

Filterability

Colloidal particles readily pass through ordinary filter papers. It is because the size of the pores of the filter paper is larger than that of the colloidal particles. Colloidal particles can often be removed by especially prepared filters of extremely small and fine porosity called ultra filters.

Concentration and density of sols

It is a rather tricky process. Most sols are fairly stable when dilute but when the volume of the dispersion medium is decreased, the colloidal particles get closer together and often combine together first to form larger particles and then finally to a coarse suspension. Chodolny has shown that the density of sols increases linearly with the concentration.

Size of the particles of the dispersed phase

Colloidal dispersions generally range in a particle size from $1\mu\text{m}$ to 1μ in a diameter. The properties which distinguish them from true solution are mainly due to their large size.

Diffusibility

Colloidal suspensions unlike true solutions do not readily diffuse through fine membranes and have a little power of diffusion.

Color

The color of the sol is not always the same as the color of the substance in the bulk. The color of the colloidal solution changes as the size and shape of the particle change.

Shape of the colloidal particles

Colloidal particles may possess very different shape and so it is very difficult to give a complete classification of colloids based on particle shape. As_2S_3 sol has spherical particles whereas $Fe(OH)_3$ sol and blue gold sol have disc or platelet like particle.

Visibility

Most of the sols appear to be true solutions with a naked eye, but the colloidal particles can be seen through an ultra microscope.

Surface area

The total surface area of the particles in colloidal system is very large, compared to an equal mass of matter in the useful coarse grained size.

Colligative properties

Sol particles because of their free suspensions amongst the molecules of the medium, share kinetic energy with them in the same manner as molecules of regular solutes do. This gives rise to colligative properties like osmotic pressure lowering, depression of freezing point and elevation of boiling point.

Viscosity of sols

It is an important property of sols because it is directly related to the shape of particles.

Surface tension

It is an important characteristic of inorganic and organic colloids. Du Nouy observed that the surface tension of many colloidal sols changes with time after the

addition of surface active agents. For example, the surface tension of a soap sol at first decreases, and then rises rapidly to its original value.

Optical properties

Colloidal sols exhibit the following noted optical properties.

(a) Optical rotation by solution of high polymers

The molecules of some organic colloids are optically active. Hence they will rotate the plane of polarized light either towards left or right.

(b) Optical anisotropy in colloids

Optical isotropic substances are those substances whose optical properties like refractive index, absorption are same in all directions. Examples are liquids, glass and cubic crystals. The optically anisotropic substances, however, exhibit different optical properties. Colloidal sols are optically anisotropic.

(c) Tyndall effect

Tyndall, in 1869, observed that when a strong beam of light is passed through a colloidal solution placed in a dark place, the path of the beam gets illuminated by a bluish light. This phenomenon is called Tyndall effect and the illuminated path is known as a Tyndall cone. The effect is due to the scattering of light by colloidal particles.

Electrical properties

An important property of colloids is that colloidal particles carry an electric charge. All the particles in a colloidal system carry the same charge (positive or negative) and the dispersion medium carries an equal but opposite kind of charge so that the system as a whole is electrically neutral. Colloidal particles move either towards the cathode or the anode under the influence of electric field, depending on the charge of the colloidal particles. The movement of colloidal particles under an applied electric field is called electrophoresis.

Brownian movement

Colloidal particles in suspension are constantly moving about in zig-zag paths. This type of erratic motion is due to the moving molecules of the dispersion medium constantly colliding with the colloidal particles. They impart momentum to colloidal particles. This random and continuing motion of colloidal particles in a dispersion medium is called Brownian movement or motion. It was named after the English Botanist Robert Brown in 1827, who noticed that pollen grains when suspended in water exhibited continued haphazard motion in all directions. Brownian movement is due to the unequal bombardment of the suspended particles by the molecules of the dispersion medium in which they are dispersed (39-40).

1.6 Applications of colloidal silver nanoparticles

1.6.1 Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy and surface enhanced resonance Raman spectroscopy

The surface enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) and especially the surface enhanced resonance Raman scattering (SERRS) are the sensitive spectroscopic techniques whose potential for the trace analysis is recently investigated. For the purpose of the SERS and SERRS analysis a range of metals (e.g. Ag, Au, Cu, Al, V, Li and Na) was tested in the form of colloidal suspensions, paper based films, silica or Teflon particles. It was found that noble metals (Ag, Au, Cu) are suitable materials when visible spectral region lasers are used, the most commonly used metal is silver. Some works suggest that only a very small fraction of silver colloid particles possess extremely high effectiveness of enhancement. These particles are called hot particles and their real SERS enhancement factor can exceed 10^{14} to 10^{15} , such enhancement corresponds to the cross section of 10^{-15} cm² per molecule. Such a high magnitude of Raman scattering enables the detection, identification and dynamic study of a single molecule adsorbed on a single colloid particle. It was found that the size of these hot particles ranges from 80 to 100 nm. Enhancement factor also depends on the shape of particles.

1.6.2 Catalytic properties

The metal colloid dispersions are commonly used as the reduction catalysts, but are rarely used as the catalysts for oxidation. The colloid silver is the exception, it is often used as the catalyst e.g. in the process of the preparation of ethylene oxide from ethylene.

Redox properties of small metallic particles differ from these properties of the bulk metal. The experiment carried out with the commonly used metals (Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Ru, Rh, Pd, Ag, Pt, Au, Hg) proved that their catalytic properties are dependent on the particle size. The research in the area of the small metal particles, redox properties is focused mainly on the stable particles in the final stage of their growth, the reports of the growing particles redox properties are scarce. During the growth of these small particles possessing renewing surface of extremely large area with excellent catalytic properties a smooth change of their redox potentials occurs.

1.6.3 The use of silver particles in sensors

The optical response of noble metal nanoparticles is often characterized by the presence of a strong absorption band that is absent from the spectrum of the bulk metal. This is attributed to a resonance in the collective motion (oscillation) of the conduction electrons in response to an incident electromagnetic field called the surface Plasmon resonance. The localisation of peak absorption wavelength λ_{max} and shape of the band depends on the particle size and shape, on the degree of their mutual interactions and local external dielectric environment. This dependence can be utilized for the development of a new class of high sensitive sensors. For e.g. the λ_{max} peak of the surface Plasmon resonance of the biotic-functionlised triangular silver nanoparticles is highly sensitive towards the chemical surroundings of the particle. Exposure of these nanoparticles to 100 nmol.dm^{-3} streptavidin caused a 27 nm red shift in λ_{max} . the detection limit of this sensor lie in the range of 10^{-12} to $10^{-13} \text{ mol.dm}^{-3}$ and prospect new ways into an ultra sensitive analysis with low requirements on the laboratory equipment.

1.6.4 Antibiotic properties

The metals which were considered endowed with magical and healing properties were gold and silver. Colloid silver is a health enhancer that acts as a powerful, all-natural antibiotic. It is comprised of submicroscopic particles of silver and silver ions that remain suspended, or colloidal, in distilled water by an electric charge placed on each particle. It is the most bioavailable form of the most effective germ killer known. While pharmaceutical antibiotics kill an average of 6 or 7 types of bacteria each, colloidal silver has been proven to kill over 650 different disease causing organisms at the UCLA Medical Labs. It is reported to be both a remedy and a preventive for colds, flu and all infections caused by any bacteria, virus, fungus or yeast. It works by disabling the enzyme that single-celled organisms need for their oxygen metabolism. Germs suffocate within 2-6 minutes of contact with silver, without any corresponding harm to human enzymes or tissues.

The anti-microbial properties of silver have been utilized since ancient times. As far back as 4000 BC, the wealthy stored their food and drinks in silver vessels to keep them fresh. They also preferred to eat with silver utensils and platters ensuring a constant trace amount of silver in their blood. Bandages and wound dressings are now often laced with silver. Colloidal silver shows great potential to wipe out diseases that are today considered incurable, such as Hepatitis C and HIV / AIDS. Numerous people have reported a complete cure from Hepatitis. C by taking adequate amounts of colloidal silver for an average of three months (41, 42).

1.7 Scope of the present study

Nanotechnology is defined as the science and engineering involved in the design, synthesis, characterization and application of materials and devices. People are interested in the nanoscale because a number of physical phenomena become noticeably pronounced as the size of the system decreases. It is at this scale the properties of materials can be very different from those at the larger scale. Larger surface area and extraordinary surface activity make these particles ideal catalysts and photo catalysts for many organic reactions. Silver nanoparticles can be used as substrates for surface

enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) studies, as an antimicrobial, to fight against bacteria and HIV virus and for wound dressing.

In the present study, colloidal silver particles were prepared by biosynthesis method. The absorption and emission properties of the synthesized colloidal silver nanoparticles are studied using UV-Visible and photoluminescence spectroscopy. Transmission electron microscopy has been used to study the morphology of the particles.

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CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

Nanotechnology is referred to as the new and advanced technology through which humans extend their ability of understanding and harnessing the nature to the atomic and molecular level by direct control and manipulation of atoms, molecules, atomic cluster or molecular clusters, causing them to recombine, rearrange, to form new substance or matter under microscopic condition i.e.; in the nanometer range. Nanotechnology is now centre-stage of the highly competitive technological developments in the world. It is a major driving force in the new age, it will bring with it drastic and widespread changes to the macro world through the control and manipulation of the microscopic environment. This is by far the most miraculous development in the history of mankind. It will have far-reaching effects on human beings, changing the world of surprise (1).

The preparation of metal and semiconductor nanoparticles has attracted considerable attention from physicists, chemists, material scientists and engineers owing to their potential applications in catalysis, biosensing, recording media and optoelectronics. Metal and semiconductor nanostructures of different sizes and shapes can now be routinely synthesized by means of various chemical and physical methods. Their performance depends critically on their size, shape and composition. Though numerous chemical methods are available for metal nanoparticles synthesis, copious reactants and starting materials are used in these reactions that are toxic and potentially hazardous. Increasing environmental concerns over chemical synthesis routes have resulted in attempts to develop bio-mimetic approaches. One of them is the synthesis using plant extracts eliminating the elaborate process of maintaining the microbial culture and often found to be kinetically favorable than other bioprocess. Bio-molecules as reducing agents are found to have a significant advantage over their counterparts as protecting agents. Environmentally benign nanoparticles synthesis procedures do not use any toxic chemicals in the synthesis protocols. In these aspects synthetic methods based

on naturally occurring biomaterials provide an alternative means for obtaining these nanoparticles (2).

A number of approaches are available for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles for example, reduction in solution, chemical and photochemical reactions in reverse micelles, thermal decomposition of silver compounds, radiation assisted, electrochemical, sonochemical, microwave assisted process and recently via green chemistry route (3).

2.2 SYNTHESIS METHODS

2.2.1 Laser ablation

Laser ablation of silver macroscopic material (e.g. silver foil) is a novel and promising physical method for the silver colloid particles preparation. The advantages of this method are an ease of the process, versatility with regard to metal identity or choice of solvent as well as the absence of additive chemical agents residues. Metal particles prepared by laser ablation are chemically pure and therefore suitable for the use in SERS as the presence of residual ions at the surface of colloidal particles significantly affects the absorption processes, particles stability and reproducibility of SERS measurement. For the purpose of SERS measurement not only the colloidal particles formed by laser ablation, but also the silver foil remaining after the process can be used. The size of the silver particles prepared by this method ranges from nanometer sizes up to 30-40 nm and depends on wavelength and intensity of the laser used, irradiation time, presence of chlorides or surfactants and the solvent in which the irradiation is carried out (6, 7).

2.2.2 The reduction by the action of ultrasound

Except for the above-mentioned usage of ultrasound in a dispersion method of colloid particle preparation it can be used also as a condensation method. The ultrasound is capable to decompose water into hydrogen and hydroxyl radicals (8-10). Subsequent reactions with suitable additives yield organic radicals which act as reducing agents. By sonification of aqueous silver salts solutions in the presence of surfactants (the frequency of ultrasound was 200 KHz) the silver particles of 13 ± 3 nm size were prepared (11).

2.2.3 Reduction by the action of gamma radiation

For the preparation of submicroscopic silver particles a direct radiolysis of silver salt aqueous solution can be used. The advantage of this preparation method is that minimum interfering chemical substances are introduced into the reaction mixture, which could possibly absorb onto particles and thus change their specific properties. During the irradiation of silver salt solution under hydrogen gas atmosphere hydrated electrons and hydrogen atoms are formed, which reduce the silver ions (12, 13). Concomitantly OH radicals, which oxidize silver particles, are formed. In the presence of hydrogen gas a part of OH radicals reacts with hydrogen molecule yielding hydrogen atoms, which contribute to silver ion reduction. By the action of this simultaneous silver ions reduction/silver particles oxidation a gradual growth is achieved, the structural defects are therefore minimized and almost monodisperse particles with average size of 7.0 nm are prepared. The course of the reduction by gamma irradiation can be influenced by other chemical agents, e.g. 2-propanol. The binding of silver ions into complex with appropriate complex agent can be the other factor usable for the influence of the reduction by gamma irradiation (14-16).

2.2.4. The reduction by the action of UV radiation

Photochemical method of colloid particle preparation using UV radiation yields the particles with properties similar to the particles produced by the above mentioned radiolytic method, its advantage being the simpler and cost effective experimental equipment. Mercury discharge lamp is often used as the source of UV radiation (17). In addition to silver salt an eventual stabilizers the reaction mixture contains suitable organic substance whose interaction with UV radiation generates radicals which reduce silver ions (18). The example of this method can be demonstrated by the system containing except for AgClO_4 , an acetone, 2-propanol and polymeric stabilizers (polyethyleneimine, sodium polyphosphate, sodium polyacrylate and polyvinylpyrrolidone). Acetone is excited by the absorption of UV radiation; the excited state reacts with 2-propanol yielding strongly reducing ketyl radicals. With polyethyleneimine as stabilizer the particles with narrow size distribution and 7 nm mean size were prepared. Acetophenon, benzophenon or ascorbic acid can be used as photo sensitive agent instead of acetone (18-20).

2.2.5 The reduction by inorganic agents

The most commonly used method for the preparation of silver sols is the reduction of silver salt by sodiumborohydride, usually following the manuscript proposed by Creighton et al, frequently used especially in the area of SERS. The procedure after Creighton et al is based on the addition of 25 ml of AgNO_3 (10^{-3} mol.dm⁻³) aqueous solution into 75 ml of the intensively stirred, ice cooled aqueous NaBH_4 (10^{-3} mol.dm⁻³) solution. Since the time of publication many modifications of Creighton procedure differing in the concentrations and molar ratios of the reactants appeared. Other factors which influence the reduction of silver salt by NaBH_4 are the temperature, the presence of surfactants, the presence of nonsaturated carboxylic acids, the presence of NaHCO_3 , the exchange of H_2O for D_2O or the method of stirring. By the standard methods of silver salt reduction by NaBH_4 the particles with units of nanometers sizes and narrow size distributions are prepared, however the preparations of larger particles is difficult (9). A modification for larger silver particles preparation was proposed by Schneider et al., in this modifications small particles are prepared by the reduction using NaBH_4 and are subsequently used as nuclei for further growth in which weaker reducing agents is used. Colloid silver can be also prepared by the reduction by hydrazine or hydrogen; depending on the experimental procedure used by silver particles with sizes ranging from units of nanometers up to several tenths of nanometers are obtained. Basic solution of hydrogen peroxide can also be used. There is a useful method of preparation of silver colloid by the reduction of silver salt solution by the complex compounds of ferrous salt (21, 22).

2.2.6 The reduction by organic reducing agents

Among reduction by organic substances the citrate reduction procedure according to Lee-Meisel is one of the most commonly used, especially for the purpose of SERS. Silver sol is prepared by the addition of 10 ml of 1% trisodium citrate into 500 ml of aqueous solution containing 90 mg of AgNO_3 . The reaction mixture is kept boiling for one hour. It was shown by spectroscopic techniques that the reduction of silver ions occurs during first two minutes after the addition of citrate, the primary particles are relatively large and polydisperse (60-80 nm). Subsequent heating of the reaction mixture leads to monodisperse particles with 27 nm average size. The reduction process can be

carried out as two stage process; the particles created in the first step can serve as the nuclei for the further growth. The silver particles can be obtained also by the well known – Tollens reagent- the silver ions in the form of ammonium complex being reduced by aldehydes or reducing sugars. Formaldehyde and sorbitol used as reducing agents give the particles with the sizes ranging from 20 to 50 nm. Colloid silver can be prepared also using ascorbic acid to reduce aqueous AgNO_3 solution. In the presence of the vinylalcohol and N-vinylpyrrolidone copolymer as additives the particles with resulting size from 3-7 nm were prepared depending on the amount of the added polymer (23).

In nonaqueous medium the solvent can serve as the reducing agent – e.g. N, N-dimethylformamide, dimethylsulfoxide or 2-propanol. The dimension of the resulting silver particles is of twenty nanometers (24).

2.3 Biosynthesis method

Biological methods of synthesis have paved way for the “greener synthesis” of nanoparticles and these have proven to be better methods due to slower kinetics, they offer better manipulation and control over crystal growth and their stabilization. This has motivated an upsurge in research on the synthesis routes that allow better control of shape and size for various nanotechnological applications. The uses of environmentally benign materials like plant extract, bacteria, fungi and enzymes for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles offer numerous benefits of eco-friendliness and compatibility for pharmaceutical and other biomedical applications as they do not use toxic chemicals for the synthesis protocol. Chemical synthesis methods lead to presence of some toxic chemical absorbed on the surface that may have adverse effect in the medical applications. Green synthesis provides advancement over chemical and physical method as it is cost effective, environment friendly, easily scaled up for large scale synthesis and in this method there is no need to use high pressure, energy, temperature and toxic chemicals.

Silver has long been recognized as having inhibitory effect on microbes present in medical and industrial process. The most important application of silver and silver nanoparticles is in medical industry such as topical ointment to prevent infection against burn and open wounds.

Here in, we report the synthesis of silver nanoparticles, reducing the silver ions present in the solution of silver nitrate by the aqueous extract of *Zingiber officinale*, leaf.

2.4 Characterization techniques

“When you can measure what you are speaking about, and express it in numbers, you know something about it; but when you cannot measure it, when you cannot express it in numbers, your knowledge is of a meager and unsatisfactory kind: it may be the beginning of knowledge, but you have scarcely, in your thoughts, advanced to the stage of science.: (5).

--- William Thomson, Lord Kelvin, Popular Lectures and Addresses (1891 – 1894)

The need to sort, name, categorize, catalog and detail the things, part and components of our world has accompanied humanity since the dawn of civilization. Characterization and reporting are fundamental to science. They are the means by which we communicate our scientific achievements. There are many types of characterization methods and most predate the advent of nanoscience and nanotechnology (5).

Characterization tools to be able to examine and see the nanostructures or the building blocks of nanomaterials, characterization tools such as X-ray diffraction, synchrotron, scanning and transmission electron microscopy, scanning tunneling and atomic force microscopy are powerful tools across disciplines (1).

In general, the role of characterization technique is to establish a correlation between the structure, shape and chemical composition of nanomaterials obtained in processing, with their properties. In the case of nanomaterials, the important aspects to consider about characterization methods are the type of information and the resolution achieved by each technique. For each nanomaterial type, one or more techniques can be used to extract the desirable information. A simple way of categorizing the characterization methods is to consider imaging and analytical techniques. Imaging involves some kind of microscopy, whereas analysis involves some type of spectroscopy (4).

In the present study the UV – Visible, photoluminescence and TEM analysis are done.

2.4.1 Ultraviolet-Visible spectroscopy

Ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy or ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometry (UV-Vis) involves the spectroscopy of photons and spectrophotometry. If a beam of light passes through a medium, the emergent radiation is always less powerful than that entering. The diminution of power is generally of different extent for different wavelength. The loss is partly due to reflections at the surfaces and partly due to scattering by the particles in the medium. But in the absence of such particles, it is primarily accounted for by the absorption of radiant energy by the medium. If the energy absorbed is greater for some visible wavelengths than for others the emergent beam will appear colored. It uses light in the visible and adjacent near ultraviolet (UV) and near infrared (NIR) ranges. In this region of energy space molecules undergo electronic transitions.

Ultraviolet and visible (UV-Vis) absorption spectroscopy is the measurement of the attenuation of a beam of light after it passes through a sample or after reflection from a sample surface. Absorption measurements can be at a single wavelength or over an extended spectral range. Ultraviolet and visible light are energetic enough to promote outer electrons to higher energy levels and UV-Vis spectroscopy is usually applied to molecules or inorganic complexes in solution. The UV-Vis spectra have broad features that are of limited use for sample identification but are very useful for quantitative measurements. The concentration of an analyte in solution can be determined by measuring the absorbance at some wavelength and applying the Beer-Lambert's law. This is the combination of two laws-Beer's law and Lambert's law. For most spectra the solution obeys Beer's law. This states that the light absorbed is proportional to the number of absorbing molecules-that is to the concentration of absorbing molecules. This is only true for dilute solutions. A second law – Lambert's law – tells us that the fraction of radiation absorbed is independent of the intensity of the radiation. Combining these two laws gives the Beer – Lambert law:

$$\text{Log}_{10} I_0 / I = \epsilon I c$$

I_0 = the intensity of the incident radiation

I = the intensity of the transmitted radiation

ϵ = the molar absorption coefficient

l = the path length of the absorbing solution (cm)

C = the concentration of the absorbing species in mol / dm³

Beer – Lamber law gives two useful informations – the molar absorption coefficient ϵ and λ_{max} which is the wavelength at which maximum absorption occurs. These two informations are enough to identify a substance. However, if ϵ and λ_{max} are known for a compound the concentration of the solution can be calculated. This is the most common application.

Since the UV-Vis range spans the range of human visual acuity of approximately 400-750 nm, UV-Vis spectroscopy is useful to characterize the absorption, transmission and reflectivity of a variety of technologically important materials, such as pigments, coatings, windows and filters. This more qualitative application usually requires recording of at least a portion of the UV-Vis spectrum for characterization of the optical or electronic properties of materials. UV-Vis spectroscopy refers to techniques where one measures how much light obey particular wavelength (color) is absorbed by a sample. Since color can often be correlated with the presence and structure of a particular chemical and since absorbance I often an easy and cheap measurement to make, absorbance spectroscopy is widely used for both qualitative, quantitative and structural work in a wide range of fields. For instance, DNA absorbs light in the UV range so the amount of DNA in a sample can be determined by measuring the absorbance of UV light. The relation between the visible color and the absorbance color is complicated; a sample that appears red does not absorb in the red, but absorbs at other wavelengths (colors) so that the light which passes through the sample is enriched in red.

The plot of amount of radiation absorbed versus wavelength for a particular compound is referred to as the absorption spectrum. The normalized absorption spectrum is characteristic for a particular compound, does not change with varying concentration and is like the chemical “fingerprint” of the compound. At wavelength corresponding to the resonant energy levels of the sample, some of the incident photons are absorbed, resulting in a drop in the measured transmission intensity and a corresponding dip in spectrum. The absorption can be measured using a spectrometer and by knowing the shape of the spectrum, the optical path length and the amount of

radiation absorbed, one can determine the structure and concentration of the compound. Visible light absorption spectra can be taken in anything that is visibly clear. Polystyrene, quartz and borosilicate (pyrex) cells, often called cuvettes, are the most commonly used. UV light is absorbed by most glasses and plastics, so quartz cells are used.

2.4.1.1 Ultraviolet-Visible spectrophotometer

The instrument used in Ultraviolet-Visible spectroscopy is called an ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer. To obtain absorption information, a sample is placed in the spectrometer and ultraviolet or visible light at a certain wavelength, or range of wavelength, is transmitted through the sample. The spectrophotometer measures how much of the light is absorbed by the sample. The intensity of light before going into a certain sample is symbolized by I_0 . The intensity of light remaining after it has gone through the sample is symbolized by I . The fraction of light transmittance is (I / I_0) , which is usually expressed as a percent of transmittance (%T). From this information, the absorbance of the sample is determined for that wavelength or as a function for a range of range of wavelengths. Sophisticated UV/Vis spectrophotometers often do this automatically.

Although the sample could be solid, or even gaseous, they are usually liquid. A transparent cell, often called a cuvette, is used to hold a liquid sample in the spectrophotometer. The pathlength L through the sample is the width of the cell through which the light passes through. Simple, economical spectrophotometers may use cuvettes shaped like cylindrical test tubes, but more sophisticated one use rectangular cuvettes, commonly 1 cm in width. For just visible spectroscopy, ordinary glass cuvettes may be used, but ultraviolet spectroscopy requires special cuvettes made of an ultraviolet-transparent material such as quartz.

The components of a typical spectrometer are shown in the following diagram. The functioning of the instrument is relatively straightforward. A beam of light from a visible and/or UV light source is separated into its component wavelength by a prism or diffraction grating. Each monochromatic (single wavelength) beam in turn is split into two equal intensity beams by a half-mirrored device. One beam, the sample beam passes through a small transparent solvent. The other beam, the reference passes through an

identical cuvette containing only the solvent. The intensities of these light beams are then measured by electronic detectors and compared. The intensity of the reference beam, which should have suffered little or no light absorption, is defined as I_0 . The intensity of the sample beam is defined as I . Over a short period of time, the spectrometer automatically scans all the component wavelength in this manner described. The ultraviolet (UV) region scanned is normally from 200 to 400 nm, and the visible portion is from 400 to 800 nm.

Schematic diagram of a double beam UV-VIS

If the sample compound does not absorb light of a given wavelength, then $I = I_0$. However, if the sample compound absorbs light then I is less than I_0 , and this difference may be plotted on a graph versus wavelength. Absorption may be presented as transmittance ($T = I/I_0$) or absorbance ($A = \log I_0/I$). If no absorption has occurred, $T = 1.0$ and $A = 0$. Most spectrometers display absorbance on the vertical axis, and the commonly observed range is from 0 (100% transmittance) to 2 (1% transmittance). The wavelength of maximum absorbance is a characteristic value, designed as λ_{max} . Different compounds may have very different absorption maxima and absorbances.

2.4.2 Transmission electron microscopy

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) is an imaging technique whereby a beam of electrons is transmitted through a specimen. An image is formed from the interaction of the electrons transmitted through the specimen; the image is magnified and focused onto an imaging device, such as a fluorescent screen, on a layer of photographic film, or to be detected by a scanner such as a CCD camera.

TEMs are capable of imaging at a significantly higher resolution than light microscopes, owing to the small de Broglie wavelength of electrons. This enables the instrument's user to examine fine detail – even as small as a single column of atoms, which is tens of thousands times smaller than the smallest resolvable object in a light microscope. TEM forms a major analysis method in a range of scientific fields, in both physical and biological sciences. TEMs find application in cancer research, virology, materials science as well as pollution and semiconductor research.

At smaller magnifications TEM image contrast is due to absorption of electrons in the material, due to the thickness and composition of the material. At higher magnifications complete wave interactions modulate the intensity of the image, requiring expert analysis of observed images. Alternate modes of use allow for the TEM to observe modulations in chemical identify, crystal orientation, electronic structure and sample induced electron phase shifts as well as the regular absorption based imaging.

The first TEM was built by Max Knoll and Ernst Ruska in 193.

The original form of Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) involves a high voltage electron beam emitted by a cathode and formed by magnetic lenses. The electron beam that has been partially transmitted through the very thin specimen carries information about the inner structure of the specimen. The spatial variation in this information (the “image”) is then magnified by a series of magnetic lenses until it is recorded by hitting a fluorescent screen, photographic plate, or light sensitive sensor such as a CCD (charge-coupled device) camera. The image detected by the CCD may be displayed in real time on a monitor or computer.

Resolution of the high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) is limited by spherical aberration and chromatic aberration, but a new generation of aberration correctors has been able to overcome spherical aberration. Software correction of spherical aberration has allowed the production of images with sufficient resolution. The ability to determine the positions of atoms within materials has made the HRTEM an indispensable tool for nano-technologies research and development in many fields, including heterogeneous catalysis and the development of semiconductor devices for electronics and photonics. Transmission electron microscopes produce two-dimensional images.

A TEM works like a slide projector. A projector shines a beam of light through the slide, as the light passes through it is affected by the structures and objects on the slide. These effects result in only certain parts of the light beam being transmitted through certain parts of the slide. This transmitted beam is then projected onto the viewing screen, forming an enlarged image of the slide. TEMs work the same way except that they shine a beam of electrons (like the light) through the specimen (like the slide). Whatever part is transmitted is projected onto a phosphor screen for the user to see. A more technical explanation of TEMs working is as follows.

The “Virtual Source” at the top represents the electron gun, producing a stream of monochromatic electrons. This stream is focused to a small, thin, coherent beam by the use of condenser lenses 1 and 2. The first lens (usually controlled by the “spot size knob”) largely determines the “spot size”; the general size range of the final spot that strikes the sample. The second lens usually controlled by the “intensity or brightness knob” actually changes the size of the spot on the sample; changing it from a wide dispersed spot to a pinpoint beam. The beam is restricted by the condenser aperture (usually user selectable), knocking out high angle electrons (those far from the optic axis, the dotted line down the center). The beam strikes the specimen and parts of it are transmitted. Thus transmitted portion is focused by the objective lens into an image. Optional Objective and Selected Area metal apertures can restrict the beam; the Objective aperture enhancing contrast by blocking out high-angle diffracted electrons, the Selected Area aperture enabling the user to examine the periodic diffraction of electrons by ordered arrangements of atoms in the sample. The image is passed down the column through the intermediate and projector lenses, being enlarged all the way. The image strikes the phosphor image screen and light is generated, allowing the user to see the image. The darker areas of the image represent those areas of the sample that fewer electrons were transmitted through (they are thicker or denser). The lighter areas of the image represent those areas of the sample that more electrons were transmitted through (they are thinner or less dense).

Limitations of the TEM procedure

- 1) Extensive sample preparation is time consuming and this limits the number of samples that can be imaged and analyzed.
- 2) In addition to the small physical size of samples, the field of view is relatively small as well.

For e.g.; the selection under analysis may not be representative of the sample as a whole.

- 3) Sample structure and morphology have been known to change drastically under exposure to electrons with extremely high energy and damage to biological samples, in particular can occur.
- 4) TEM is a high-vacuum instrument that is costly to operate and to maintain, certainly playing a role in the high barrier entry required to conduct nanoscience research

However, the advantages of the TEM techniques are numerous. Any type of sample, whether electrically insulating, semiconducting or conducting, is able to be imaged by TEM. The incredible resolution capability allows for atomic level inspection (5).

2.4.3 X-Ray Diffraction

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) is a rapid analytical technique primarily used for phase identification of a crystalline material and can provide information on unit cell dimensions. The analyzed material is finely ground, homogenized, and average bulk composition is determined. Max von Laue, in 1912, discovered that crystalline substances act as three-dimensional diffraction gratings for X-ray wavelengths similar to the spacing of planes in a crystal lattice. X-ray diffraction is now a common technique for the study of crystal structures and atomic spacing.

X-ray diffraction is based on constructive interference of monochromatic X-rays and a crystalline sample. These X-rays are generated by a cathode ray tube, filtered to produce monochromatic radiation, collimated to concentrate, and directed toward the sample.

The interaction of the incident rays with the sample produces constructive interference (and a diffracted ray) when conditions satisfy Bragg's Law ($n\lambda=2d \sin \theta$). This law relates the wavelength of electromagnetic radiation to the diffraction angle and the lattice spacing in a crystalline sample.

These diffracted X-rays are then detected, processed and counted. By scanning the sample through a range of 2θ angles, all possible diffraction directions of the lattice should be attained due to the random orientation of the powdered material. Conversion of the diffraction peaks to d-spacings allows identification of the mineral because each mineral has a set of unique d-spacings. Typically, this is achieved by comparison of d-spacings with standard reference patterns.

X-ray diffractometers consist of three basic elements: an X-ray tube, a sample holder, and an X-ray detector. X-rays are generated in a cathode ray tube by heating a filament to produce electrons, accelerating the electrons toward a target by applying a voltage, and bombarding the target material with electrons. When electrons have

sufficient energy to dislodge inner shell electrons of the target material, characteristic X-ray spectra are produced. These spectra consist of several components, the most common being K_{α} and K_{β} . K_{α} consists, in part, of $K_{\alpha 1}$ and $K_{\alpha 2}$. $K_{\alpha 1}$ has a slightly shorter wavelength and twice the intensity as $K_{\alpha 2}$. The specific wavelengths are characteristic of the target material (Cu, Fe, Mo and Cr). Filtering, by foils or crystal monochrometers, is required to produce monochromatic X-rays needed for diffraction. $K_{\alpha 1}$ and $K_{\alpha 2}$ is sufficiently close in wavelength such that a weighted average of the two is used. Copper is the most common target material for single-crystal diffraction, with CuK_{α} radiation = 1.5418Å.

These X-rays are collimated and directed onto the sample. As the sample and detector are rotated, the intensity of the reflected X-rays is recorded. When the geometry of the incident X-rays impinging the sample satisfies the Bragg Equation, constructive interference occurs and a peak in intensity occurs. A detector records and processes this X-ray signal and converts the signal to a count rate which is then output to a device such as a printer or computer monitor.

The geometry of an X-ray diffractometer is such that the sample rotates in the path of the collimated X-ray beam at an angle θ while the X-ray detector is mounted on an arm to collect the diffracted X-rays and rotates at an angle of 2θ . The instrument used to maintain the angle and rotate the sample is termed *goniometer*. For typical powder patterns, data is collected at 2θ from $\sim 5^{\circ}$ to 70° , angles that are preset in the X-ray scan.

The particle size of the prepared samples was determined by using Scherrer's equation as follows $D \approx 0.9\lambda/\beta \cos\theta$, where D is crystal size, λ is the wavelength of X-ray, θ is the Bragg's angle and β is the full width at half maximum of the peak in radians.

2.4.4 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

To put the nanoscale in a more understandable perspective, consider that the size of an atom relative to an apple is similar to the size of an apple relative to the planet Earth! Atomic Force Microscopes (AFMs) give us a window into this nanoscale world.

Principle and technique

- **Surface Sensing**

An AFM uses a cantilever with a very sharp tip to scan over a sample surface. As the tip approaches the surface, the close-range, attractive force between the surface and the tip cause the cantilever to deflect towards the surface. However, as the cantilever is brought even closer to the surface, such that the tip makes contact with it, increasingly repulsive force takes over and causes the cantilever to deflect away from the surface.

- **Detection Method**

A laser beam is used to detect cantilever deflections towards or away from the surface. By reflecting an incident beam off the flat top of the cantilever, any cantilever deflection will cause slight changes in the direction of the reflected beam. A position-sensitive photo diode (PSPD) can be used to track these changes. Thus, if an AFM tip passes over a raised surface feature, the resulting cantilever deflection (and the subsequent change in direction of reflected beam) is recorded by the PSPD.

- **Imaging**

An AFM images the topography of a sample surface by scanning the cantilever over a region of interest. The raised and lowered features on the sample surface influence the deflection of the cantilever, which is monitored by the PSPD. By using a feedback loop to control the height of the tip above the surface—thus maintaining constant laser position—the AFM can generate an accurate topographic map of the surface features.

2.4.5 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

It is a technique which is used to obtain an infrared spectrum of absorption or emission of a solid, liquid or gas. An FTIR spectrometer simultaneously collects high spectral resolution data over a wide spectral range. This confers a significant advantage over a dispersive spectrometer which measures intensity over a narrow range of wavelengths at a time.

The term *Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy* originates from the fact that a Fourier transform (a mathematical process) is required to convert the raw data into the actual spectrum. FTIR offers quantitative and qualitative analysis for organic and inorganic samples. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) identifies chemical bonds in a molecule by producing an infrared absorption spectrum. The spectra produce a profile of the sample, a distinctive molecular fingerprint that can be used to screen and scan samples for many different components. FTIR is an effective analytical instrument for detecting functional groups and characterizing covalent bonding information.

FTIR can be used with other molecular spectroscopy techniques available, including Diffuse Reflectance Infrared Fourier Transform Spectroscopy (DRIFTS), Infrared-spectroscopy coupled to Thermo gravimetric Analysis (FTIR/TGA), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (NMR), Gas Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS), Liquid Chromatography - Mass Spectrometry (LC/MS), UV/Vis spectroscopy, Near Infra Red (NIR) and Raman scattering. FTIR combined with these techniques provides complementary data regarding a molecule's molecular structure. It is powerful tool for isolating and characterizing organic contamination.

FTIR is the fact that the most molecules absorb light in the infra-red region of the electromagnetic spectrum. This absorption corresponds to the bonds present in the molecule. The frequency range is measured as wave numbers typically over the range 4000 – 600 cm^{-1} . The background emission spectrum of the IR source is first recorded, followed by the emission spectrum of the IR source with the sample in place. The ratio of the sample spectrum to the background spectrum is directly related to the sample's absorption spectrum. The resultant absorption spectrum from the bond natural vibration frequencies indicates the presence of various chemical bonds and functional groups present in the sample. FTIR is particularly useful for identification of organic molecular groups and compounds due to the range of functional groups, side chains and cross-links involved, all of which will have characteristic vibration frequencies in the infra-red rang.

2.4.6 Apoptosis

There are two ways that a cell can die: necrosis and apoptosis. **Necrosis** occurs when a cell is damaged by an external force, such as poison, a bodily injury, an infection

or getting cut off from the blood supply (which might occur during a heart attack or stroke). When cells die from necrosis, it's a rather messy affair. The death causes inflammation that can cause further distress or injury within the body.

Apoptosis, on the other hand, is relatively civil, even though it may not sound so at first -- it's when a cell commits suicide. How is that better than necrosis? For one thing, the cleanup is much easier. It's sometimes referred to as **programmed cell death**, and indeed, the process of apoptosis follows a controlled, predictable routine.

When a cell is compelled to commit suicide (we'll get to the triggers for apoptosis in just a minute), proteins called caspases go into action. They break down the cellular components needed for survival, and they spur production of enzymes known as DNases, which destroy the DNA in the nucleus of the cell. It's like roadies breaking down the stage in an arena after a major band has been through town. The cell shrinks and sends out distress signals, which are answered by vacuum cleaners known as macrophages. The macrophages clean away the shrunken cells, leaving no trace, so these cells have no chance to cause the damage that necrotic cells do.

Apoptosis also differs from necrosis in that it's essential to human development. For example, in the womb, our fingers and toes are connected to one another by a sort of webbing. Apoptosis is what causes that webbing to disappear, leaving us with 10 separate digits. As our brains develop, the body creates millions more cells than it needs;

the ones that don't form synaptic connections undergo apoptosis so that the remaining cells function well. Programmed cell death is also necessary to start the process of menstruation.

That's not to say that apoptosis is a perfect process. Sometimes, the wrong cells kill themselves off, and sometimes, the ones that should say "auf Wiedersehen" stick around instead. This brings us to our discussion of the triggers of apoptosis. Rather than dying due to injury, cells that go through apoptosis die in response to signals within the body. When cells recognize viruses and gene mutations, they may induce death to prevent the damage from spreading. When cells are under stress, as may happen when free radicals are on the loose or when a person undergoes radiation, apoptosis can occur. But there are also signals within the body that send the message that a cell should continue living. All cells have varying level of sensitivity to the positive and negative triggers, so sometimes the wrong cells live and die.

Scientists are trying to learn how they can modulate apoptosis, so that they can control which cells live and which undergo programmed cell death. Anti-cancer drugs and radiation, for example, work by triggering apoptosis in diseased cells. Many diseases and disorders are linked with the life and death of cells -- increased apoptosis is a characteristic of AIDS, Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease, while decreased apoptosis can signal lupus or cancer. Understanding how to regulate apoptosis could be the first step to treating these conditions. (10,12)

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CHAPTER 3

GREEN SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES USING STERCULIA QUADRIFIDA LEAF EXTRACT

3.1 Introduction

Bio-nanosynthesis has become a potential resource for the development and progress of humanity. The present article reports a bio-synthetic pathway for the production of highly stable, bio-inspired silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using fresh *Sterculia quadrifida* leaves. The method is simple, cost-effective, eco-friendly, facile and reproducible. The reduction of silver ions and the formation of bio-genic silver nanoparticles has been monitored using UV–Visible spectroscopy. Zeta analysis and DLS studies are employed to determine the stability and average size of the AgNPs. AFM, TEM and XRD results reveal the size, morphology and crystalline nature of silver nanoparticles. FTIR analysis helped to identify the biomolecules that bind on the surface of silver nanoparticles and increase the stability of the particles. *Sterculia quadrifida* extract proved to be an excellent reducing agent of silver ions and the biosynthesized AgNPs are biodegradable and environment friendly. Antimicrobial and anticancerous studies were also conducted.

Nanoscience has paved way for creation and manipulation of ultra-small structures or materials at atomic, molecular and macromolecular scales, where properties differ significantly from those at a larger scale. Nanoscience and nanotechnology has revolutionised the present era and helped mankind to make a giant leap into the future. For instance, the advent of metal nanoparticles exhibited remarkable potential for numerous applications, especially in electronics and catalysts, sensing, optics, magnetism, mechanics, robotics, data storage and biomedical applications. Among various noble metal nanoparticles, silver nanoparticles have gained utmost importance due to their size, distribution and morphology. Precise control over these attributes help to determine the physical properties of silver nanoparticles including the Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR). Colloidal silver also exhibits antimicrobial and anticancerous activities.

Several approaches are in practice for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles such as electrochemical, sonochemical and microwave assisted processes, but most of these strategies consist of utilization of high energy, hazardous chemicals and are difficult. Green chemistry has attained To switch over these technical hitches, biological methods have been incorporated with green chemistry route which is eco-friendly approach in the synthesis process. The use of plant materials for the synthesis of nanoparticles could be more advantageous, because it does not require elaborate processes. Biomolecules like proteins, phenols and flavonoids present in plants play a pivotal role in the reduction of silver particles.

In this paper, we report for the first time the synthesis of silver nanoparticles by the reduction of aqueous silver ions with the use of aqueous extract of *Sterculia quadrifida* leaves. *Sterculia quadrifida*(fig. 1a) is a medicinal plant which is a source of secondary metabolites and is also well known for its phenolic content. Its leaves (fig. 1b) are used for treating sore eyes and have gained reputation for its antibacterial and antioxidant activities as well. So far, there have been no reports on the synthesis of nanoparticles by using leaf extract. Therefore, the present report is on the synthesis of extracellular formation of AgNPs at room temperature using the aqueous extract of young leaves of *Sterculia quadrifida* as a simple, low cost and reproducible method. (1,2)

3.2. Materials and Methods

3.2.1 Chemicals and plant material collection

Silver nitrate (AgNO_3) of A.R grade was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich with $\geq 99.5\%$ purity from India. All glassware were cleaned with aqua regia and rinsed several times with de-ionised water.

Fresh young leaves of *Sterculia quadrifida* were collected locally in the month of April 2016.

3.2.2 Biological and phytochemical characteristics of leaves

Fig. 1a Sterculia quadrifida

Fig. 1b Sterculia quadrifida leaves

Sterculia quadrifida

Scientific classification

Kingdom: Plantae
Phylum: Angiosperms
Class: Eudicots
Subclass: Rosids
Order: Malvales
Family: Malvaceae
Genus: Sterculia
Species: S.quadrifida

Phytochemical constituents of Sterculia quadrifida leaf extract

Constituents	Water extract
Alkaloids	Absent
Carbohydrates	Present
Glycosides	Absent
Steroids	Absent
Flavanoids	Present
Phenols	Present
Saponins	Present
Tannins	Present
Amino acids	Present

3.3 Preparation of the extract

Fresh leaves of *Sterculia quadrifida* were collected locally and 50 g of young leaves were washed initially with tap water, and then surface washed with de-ionised water several times until no impurities remained. The dirt free leaves were cut into fine pieces. The pieces of *Sterculia quadrifida* leaves were then taken into 1000 ml beaker containing 250 ml deionised water and boiled at 373 K for 15 min. The raw extract obtained was filtered twice with Whatman filter paper No. 42 (pore size 0.45 μm and 0.22 μm sized). The filtered extract was collected and used fresh for further studies. This filtrate was used for the reduction of Ag^+ to Ag^0 .

3.4 Synthesis of Silver nanoparticles from *Sterculia quadrifida* leaf extract

Freshly prepared aqueous solution of 1mM silver nitrate (AgNO_3) was used for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles. . 1mL of aqueous leaf extract was added to 10mL of AgNO_3 solution with constant stirring for 10 minutes so as to obtain bio-genic AgNPs (sample A1) at room temperature. The formation of silver nanoparticles was indicated by the appearance of yellowish brown color within 8 minutes. Samples A2, A3, A4 and A5 were synthesized using the same procedure by adding 1.5 mL, 2 mL, 2.5 mL and 3mL extracts respectively. (3,5)

Characterization of synthesized silver nanoparticle

The characterization study of silver nanoparticles involved qualitative and quantitative analysis of the synthesized particles. The following techniques were employed:

a) Visual examination

Color of the leaf extract was noted prior to the synthesis of AgNPs. A visible color change (yellow-reddish brown) during the experiment indicated the formation of bio-genic AgNPs.(6,7)

b) UV- Visible spectra analysis

The formation of AgNPs was verified by using JASCO UV–visible spectrophotometer (model: V-650) operated at with 0.1 nm resolution with optical length of 10 mm. Deionised water was used for baseline correction in UV–visible absorption spectra. UV–visible spectral analysis was performed for all samples and the absorption maxima were recorded at a wavelength of 300-550 nm.

c) Zeta potential analysis

Zeta potential analysis was employed to attain information about the stability of nanoparticles and surface charge. (8)

d) Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) analysis

The images of atomic force microscope (AFM) were collected under ambient conditions on a Veeco-Innova scanning probe microscope etched Si– nano probe tips (RTESPA-M) were used for the same. (8)

e) Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) analysis

TEM was used to obtain the shape and crystal structure (if any) as well as size of the particles in the bulk. The transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were obtained using Technai-20 Philips instrument operated at 190 keV. Sample for this analysis were prepared by Rapid Biosynthesis of Silver Nanoparticles Using *Sterculia quadrifida* 109 coating of aqueous AgNPs drops on carbon coated copper grids, kept for 5 min; the extra solution was removed using blotting paper. The film of TEM grid is exposed to IR light for drying. (9,10)

f) X-ray-diffraction (XRD) analysis

The bio-genic AgNPs solution was purified by repeated centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 20 minutes followed by redispersion of the pellet of silver nanoparticles into 10 ml of deionized water. After freeze drying of the purified silver particles, the dried mixture was collected for determination of the structure and composition of Ag nanoparticles by an X'Pert Pro x-ray diffractometer operated at a voltage of 40 kV and a current of 30 mA with Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) radiation.(9,10)

g) Fourier Transforms Infra-Red Spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis

The powder sample of AgNPs was prepared by centrifuging the biosynthesized AgNPs solution at 5,000 rpm for 10 minutes so as to remove any free biomass residue or adhering compound that is not the capping ligand of the nanoparticles. The resulting suspension was redispersed in 10 ml sterile distilled water. The centrifuging and redispersing process was repeated three times and the purified suspension was freeze dried to obtain dried powder. Finally, the dried nanoparticles were analyzed by FTIR Spectrometer – BRUKER Optik GmbH TENSOR 27. (11,12)

h) Antimicrobial studies (Antibacterial studies)

Since silver and its salts exhibit strong antibacterial activity, this property was evaluated for the Ag-nanoparticles prepared.

(I) Culturing and Preservation of Bacteria

The conventional cup-plate method was used to determine the antibacterial activity of biologically prepared Ag-nanoparticles. It's a screening test generally done for verifying antimicrobial activity of samples. For performing the experiment, cultures of test bacterial strains- *Bacillus subtilis* (a Gram-positive bacterium) and *Escherichia coli* (a Gram-negative bacterium), were collected from Microbiology Department, Bishop Moore College, Mavelikara. The strains were grown and preserved in the culture media following standard procedures.

(i) Preparing an enriched medium

The medium for selective growth of a bacterial strain may differ for various bacteria but each medium must contain certain components which should support growth by providing the basic elements needed for growth and the source of energy. In this

study, Nutrient Agar medium was used which supports growth of a wide range of bacteria including *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli*.

For 100 ml Nutrient Agar medium, 2.8 g Nutrient agar powder was added in 100 ml distilled water; for the cup-plate method, 0.5 g of agar powder was added in addition to the medium. The medium kept in cotton-plugged glass container was sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 15 mins. It was distributed inside a laminar hood either in culture tubes or on Petri dishes when hot (about 45°C) and allowed to solidify.

(ii) Serial subculture

Microorganisms should be preserved in a manner that will allow their long-term survival and genetic stability. The method of preservation depends on the organism. Subculturing in a suitable gelled medium after intervals is a popular method for the preservation of bacteria. Serial subculture in liquid medium is also a simple method where cultures are transferred to fresh medium of same type and allowed to grow in an incubator at 38°C. We mentioned the bacterial strains in both liquid and gelled medium.

(iii) Evaluation of antibacterial activity of Ag-nanoparticles by cup-plate method

Nutrient agar medium (25 ml) was taken in two 100-ml Erlenmeyer flasks and sterilized. After cooling the medium at about 45°C, freshly grown liquid culture (0.25 ml) of *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli* was added in either of the flask, mixed thoroughly but quickly, and poured in four (two for each bacterium) Petri dishes equally. The dishes were kept at room temperature in a laminar hood. After the medium was solidified, three cups of approx. 0.5 cm diameter were made by a cork-borer at three corners of each Petri dish at about 1.5 cm away from the disk-wall. Occasionally some liquid may come out from the gelled medium in the cups, which is removed by aspiration by a Pasteur pipette or a micro-pipette. Thereafter, samples were added in each well of each Petri dish.

The Petri dishes were marked as D1, D2, D3 and D4; the cups were also marked as well. D1 and D2 were seeded with *B. subtilis* whereas D3 and D4 with *E. coli*. As control, 0.1 ml of sterile leaf extract was added in one cup in D1; in two other cups of D1, 0.1 ml of silver nitrate and leaf extract mixture with 10.0 mM and 3.33 mM concentrations respectively were added. In D2, suspension of AgNPs was added in one

cup and the mixture of silver nitrate and fruit extract with 10 mM and 3.33 mM respectively were added in two other cups. The same combination of samples was applied in D3 and D4 where *E. coli* was seeded. The suspension of Ag-nanoparticles was prepared by ultracentrifugation of the clear supernatant derived from the mixture of 10 mM AgNO₃ solution with the leaf extract after 48 hours incubation as described before.

After adding the samples in the cups, the dishes were kept in a refrigerator for an hour for proper absorption of the samples into the surrounding medium from the well. The plates were then transferred into an incubator set at 38⁰C to allow bacterial growth on the medium. After 24 hrs the plates were taken out of the incubator and observed for zone of bacterial growth inhibition around the cups.

(iv) Formation of the 'Zone of Inhibition'

After 24 hours of incubation at 38⁰C, distinct zone of bacterial growth inhibition was observed around all the experimental and positive control cups whereas no such zone was formed around the cups containing leaf extract only. The results strongly suggest that silver nanoparticles possess antibacterial activity similar to AgNO₃. The particles show activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains used in this study though the inhibition zone appears better in case of the Gram-negative bacterium, *E. coli*.

i) Anticancerous studies

• Invitro Antiproliferative Effect Determination By MTT Assay

SW480 (Colon carcinoma) cell line was initially procured from National Centre for Cell Sciences (NCCS), Pune, India and maintained Dulbecos modified Eagles medium (Gibco, Invitrogen).

The cell line was cultured in 25 cm² tissue culture flask with DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS, L-glutamine, sodium bicarbonate and antibiotic solution containing: Penicillin (100U/ml), Streptomycin (100µg/ml), and Amphotericin B (2.5µg/ml). Cultured cell lines were kept at 37⁰C in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator (NBS Eppendorf, Germany). The viability of cells were evaluated by direct observation of cells by Inverted phase contrast microscope and followed by MTT assay method.

Cells seeding in 96 well plate:

Two days old confluent monolayer of cells were trypsinized and the cells were suspended in 10% growth medium, 100µl cell suspension (5×10^4 cells/well) was seeded in 96 well tissue culture plate and incubated at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator.

Cytotoxicity Evaluation:

After 24 hours , the samples (A1,A2,A3,A4 andA5) each volume of 10µl were added in triplicates to the respective wells and incubated at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator.

Cytotoxicity Assay by Direct Microscopic observation:

Entire plate was observed at an interval of each 24 hours; up to 72 hours in an inverted phase contrast tissue culture microscope (Olympus CKX41 with Optika Pro5 CCD camera) and microscopic observation were recorded as images. Any detectable changes in the morphology of the cells, such as rounding or shrinking of cells, granulation and vacuolization in the cytoplasm of the cells were considered as indicators of cytotoxicity. (11,13)

Cytotoxicity Assay by MTT Method:

Fifteen mg of MTT (Sigma, M-5655) was reconstituted in 3 ml PBS until completely dissolved and sterilized by filter sterilization.

After 24 hours of incubation period, the sample content in wells were removed and 3 0µl of reconstituted MTT solution was added to all test and cell control wells, the plate was gently shaken well, then incubated at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator for 4 hours. After the incubation period, the supernatant was removed and 100µl of MTT Solubilization Solution (DMSO was added and the wells were mixed gently by pipetting up and down in order to solubilize the formazan crystals.

The absorbance values were measured by using microplate reader at a wavelength of 570 nm (Laura B. Talarico et al., 2004).

The percentage of growth inhibition was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ of viability} = \frac{\text{Mean OD Samples} \times 100}{\text{OD of control group}}$$

- **Invitro Cytotoxic Effect Determination By MTT Assay**

L929 (fibroblast) cell line was initially procured from National Centre for Cell Sciences (NCCS), Pune, India and maintained Dulbecos modified Eagles medium (Gibco, Invitrogen).

The cell lines were cultured in 25 cm² tissue culture flask with DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS, , L-glutamine, sodium bicarbonate and antibiotic solution containing: Penicillin (100U/ml), Streptomycin (100µg/ml), and Amphotericin B (2.5µg/ml). Cultured cell lines were kept at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator (NBS Eppendorf, Germany). The viability of cells were evaluated by direct observation of cells by Inverted phase contrast microscope and followed by MTT assay method.

- **Determination Of Apoptosis By Acridine Orange (AO) And Ethidium Bromide (EB) Double Staining.**

DNA-binding dyes AO and EB (Sigma, USA) were used for the morphological detection of apoptotic and necrotic cells (Zhang et al, 1998). AO is taken up by both viable and non-viable cells and emits green fluorescence if intercalated into double stranded nucleic acid (DNA). EB is taken up only by non-viable cells and emits red fluorescence by intercalation into DNA. The cells were cultured in Dulbeccos modified Eagles media and grown to 60-70% confluency and treated at a final volume of 10µl (sample- A1) for 24 h, the cells were washed by cold PBS and then stained with a mixture of AO (100 µg/ml) and EB (100 µg/ml) at room temperature for 10min. The stained cells were washed twice with 1X PBS and observed by a fluorescence microscope in blue filter of fluorescent microscope (Olympus CKX41 with Optika Pro5 camera). . The cells were divided into four categories as follows: living cells (normal green nucleus), early apoptotic (bright green nucleus with condensed or fragmented chromatin), late apoptotic (orange-stained nuclei with chromatin condensation or fragmentation) and necrotic cells (uniformly orange-stained cell nuclei). (12,15)

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a) Visual examination

The leaf extract had a pale yellow color and appeared turbid soon after adding AgNO₃. The intensity of the color increased gradually from pale yellow to dark brown with passage of time and finally attained reddish brown color at the end of the experiment.

The appearance of dark reddish brown color of silver nanoparticles is due to the coherent excitation of all the “free” electrons within the conduction band, leading to a phase oscillation and is a clear indication of the formation of silver nanoparticles in the reaction. There is no significant change beyond 240 minutes, thereby indicating the completion of the reduction reaction. This was further confirmed by UV-Vis spectroscopic analysis.

The digital photograph of samples A1-A5 is shown in Fig. a.

Fig a. Biosynthesized silver nanoparticles

b) UV- Visible spectral analysis

UV-visible absorption spectroscopy is one of the most important techniques used for characterization of optical properties and electronic structure of nanoparticles. It is used to ascertain the formation and stability of metal nanoparticles in aqueous solution.

Silver nanoparticles usually exhibit a UV-Visible absorption peak in the range 400-500nm. The formation of AgNPs was initially confirmed using UV- Visible spectroscopy which is attributed to the phenomenon of “Surface Plasmon Resonance phenomenon”. Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) is the coherent excitation of free electrons within the conduction band leading to an in-phase oscillation. The plays a crucial role in determining the polarizability of the metal and therefore shifts the resonance to optical frequencies.

The UV-visible absorption spectra of as prepared silver nanoparticles are shown in Fig. b

Fig.b The UV-visible absorption spectra

The SPR band of sample A1 appears at 434 nm with a low intensity. The SPR band of A2–A5 samples appears at 423 nm, 425 nm, 423 nm, 419 nm respectively. The absorption maximum increases with the volume of extract, mainly due to the formation of more nanoparticles. The broad SPR at lower volumes of extract can be attributed to the formation of anisotropic particles. Also, more symmetrical SPR band is observed with larger quantity of extract. This also supports the strong reducing property of *Sterculia quadrifida* leaf extract.

c) Zeta potential analysis

Zeta potential analysis is employed to evaluate the stability of bio-synthesized AgNPs as shown below. AgNPs displayed an increase in the zeta potential value with increase in the quantity of leaf extract.

Sample A1: Apparent zeta potential= -14.8 m V

Sample A2: Apparent zeta potential= -18.6 m V

Sample A3: Apparent zeta potential= -20.02 m V

Sample A4: Apparent zeta potential= -23 m V

Sample A5: Apparent zeta potential= -24.2 m V

The zeta potential value specifically increased from -14.8 mV to -24.2 mV for A1 to A5 colloids which expound the increased stability of the prepared AgNPs with the increase of extract quantity. The high negative values indicate repulsion among the particles and thereby attainment of better stability avoiding agglomeration. This ensures a longer lifetime for the bio-genic samples without spoilage.

d) AFM

AFM analysis is one of the most sophisticated tools, often employed to understand the morphology of bio-genic Ag NPs particles. Small volume of AgNPs sample was spread on a well-cleaned glass cover slip surface mounted on the AFM stub, and was dried with nitrogen flow at room temperature. Images were obtained in tapping mode using a silicon probe cantilever of $125\mu\text{m}$ length, resonance frequency 210-290 kHz, spring constant 20-80 nm. The images obtained are shown below:

Fig d: AFM image showing AgNPs (2D)

Fig d: AFM image showing AgNPs (3D)

AFM image confirms the spherical shape of the particles and again the tendency for particles to aggregate. The average size of particles was found to be 15-20nm.

e) TEM

Transmission Electron Microscopy offers the highest resolution we can achieve. This method helps us to observe the particle size of a material in nano-dimension and study

the crystal structure meticulously. The TEM images of Ag NPs synthesized in room temperature (25_C) were shown in Fig. 5. The sizes distribution of Ag NPs synthesized at room temperature were narrow, mostly in the range of 5–25 nm. And some Ag NPs with diameters close to 50nm were observed.

Fig e: TEM image showing AgNPs (2D)

f) XRD

The crystalline nature of bio-synthesised AgNPs was confirmed from XRD analysis. Fig. 4.6. illustrates the XRD pattern of AgNPs. The XRD pattern showed three intense peaks in the whole spectrum of 2θ value ranging from 20 to 80 (particularly around 38°). The typical XRD pattern revealed that the sample contains a mixed phase (cubic and hexagonal) structures of silver nanoparticles. The average estimated particle size of this sample was 30nm. Intense Bragg reflections suggests strong X-ray scattering centres in

the crystalline phase and could be due to capping agents. Therefore, XRD results also suggested that the crystallization of the bio-organic phase occurs on the surface of the silver nanoparticles or vice versa. Generally, the broadening of peaks in the XRD patterns of solids is attributed to particle size effects. Broader peaks signify smaller particle size and reflect the effects due to experimental conditions on the nucleation and growth of the crystal nuclei. Furthermore, remaining small peaks were observed.

Fig.f. XRD Spectrum for biosynthesized silver nanoparticles

g) FTIR

FTIR spectroscopy measurements were carried out to identify the biomolecules adhering specifically on the metal surface and the local molecular environment of capping agent associated with the nanoparticles. To remove any free biomass residue or compound that is not the capping ligand of the nanoparticles, the biosynthesized AgNPs solution was centrifuged at 5,000 rpm for 10 minutes and the resulting suspension was redispersed in 10 ml sterile distilled water. The purified suspension was freeze dried to

obtain dried powder. Finally, the dried nanoparticles were analyzed by FTIR Spectrophotometer.

Fig.g FTIR Spectrum

Fig.g shows broad peak in higher energy region 3341cm^{-1} , which characterizes the polysaccharides from the extract. This absorption frequency is assigned to the OeH group. The absorption band observed at 1634 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the amide groups of protein or to the C]O stretching vibration group. The prominent band at 644 cm^{-1} is assigned to the aromatic class. Previous studies have confirmed the fact that the carbonyl group from amino acid residues and proteins has the stronger ability to bind metal, indicating that the proteins could possibly form a layer covering the metal nanoparticles to prevent agglomeration and thus increase stability.

h) Antimicrobial studies (Antibacterial studies)

The following images show zone of inhibition as observed during the experiment?

The disk D1 shows Inhibition Zone for silver nitrate with fruit extract where negative control shows no result

The disk D2 shows Inhibition Zone for silver nitrate with fruit extract where AgNPs shows the same result.

The disk D3 shows Inhibition Zone for samples of silver nitrate with fruit extract where negative control shows no result

The disk D4 shows Inhibition Zone for silver nitrate with leaf extract where AgNPs shows the same result.

The distinct Zone of Inhibition was observed around the cup wherein the suspension of AgNPs was applied as shown above. The mixtures of AgNO₃ and fruit extract with 10.0 mM and 0.33 mM concentrations also prevented the bacterial growth. The sterile juice of leaf extract showed no result. The same microbiological test was performed against two common fungi- *A. niger* and *A. wentii* but the biologically synthesized silver nanoparticles did not show any positive result.

At the end of this antimicrobial screening test, it is confirmed that the biologically synthesized Silver Nanoparticles (SNP) possess effective antibacterial property. Therefore, applications of SNPs can cover a large domain of medical, leather and food technologies. (9,10)

i) Anticancerous studies

❖ Invitro Antiproliferative Effect Determination By MTT Assay

Cytotoxicity Assay by MTT Method:

The percentage of growth inhibition was calculated and tabulated for each sample as:

Samples	Average OD at 540nm	Percentage Viability
Control	0.8809	
A1	0.404	45.86219
A2	0.4906	55.69304
A3	0.5028	57.07799
A4	0.5584	63.38972
A5	0.613	69.58792

❖ Invitro Cytotoxic Effect Determination By MTT Assay

The viability of cells were evaluated by direct observation of cells by Inverted phase contrast microscope and followed by MTT assay method and the obtained values were tabulated as follows:

Samples	Average OD at 540nm	Percentage Viability
Control	0.8897	
A1	0.8176	91.89614
A2	0.7294	81.98269
A3	0.6921	77.79027
A4	0.544	61.14421
A5	0.4896	55.02979

❖ **Determination Of Apoptosis By Acridine Orange (AO) And Ethidium Bromide (EB) Double Staining.**

The cells were divided into four categories after apoptosis was carried out:

- i. living cells (normal green nucleus)
- ii. early apoptotic (bright green nucleus with condensed or fragmented chromatin)
- iii. late apoptotic (orange-stained nuclei with chromatin condensation or fragmentation)
- iv. necrotic cells (uniformly orange-stained cell nuclei).

Fig.i (1) MTT Assay - 1

Fig.i (2) MTT Assay - 2

Fig.i (3) MTT Assay -3

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

Green synthesis of stable silver nanoparticles using *Sterculia Quadrifida leaf extract* was demonstrated. The extract enacted the roles of reductant, size controller and stabilizer at room temperature, thereby providing us with a rapid yield of bio-genic nanoparticles. The amount of extract played a crucial role in the formation of silver nanoparticles.(17,18)

Visual examination and UV-Visible spectroscopy helped in ascertaining the formation of bio-genic AgNPs. UV-Vis spectra elucidated the blue shift, intended to the decrement of particle size with extract quantity. Stability of silver nanoparticles was determined using Zeta potential analysis. XRD, AFM and TEM were employed to access the size, shape and morphological characters associated with AgNPs. The functional groups responsible for the biosorption, bioreduction and biostabilization processes during the formation of AgNPs were identified through FTIR analysis.

It was confirmed that the obtained nanoparticles were capable of rendering significant antibacterial and anticancerous efficacy and hence have potential applications in biomedical field.

Finally, this procedure proved to have several advantages such as simplicity, eco-friendliness, cost-effectiveness, reproducibility, compatibility for medical and pharmaceutical applications as well as large scale commercial production.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION

SEC	Size Exclusion Chromatography
UV-Vis	Ultraviolet-Visible Spectroscopy
DLS	Dynamic Light Scattering
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
AgNP	Silver nanoparticles
nm	Nanometer
mV	Millivolt
rpm	Rotation per minute

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